

Analysis of community coordination strategies and their economic impacts on energy communities

Josh Eichman^{a,b}, Mariana Jiménez Martínez^a, and Cristina Corchero^{c,a}

^a Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, 2, 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs (Barcelona), Spain; jeichman@irec.cat (CA)

^b National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Golden, Colorado, USA; joshua.eichman@nrel.gov

^c Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech (UPC), Jordi Girona, 1-3, 08034 Barcelona (Barcelona), Spain; cristina.corchero@upc.edu

Abstract:

Energy communities represent a promising mechanism to accelerate the energy transition. It is clear from the growing body of legislation, and investment in research, development, and deployment of renewable energy communities that there is strong interest and great potential in enabling energy communities. An assessment of the economic benefit of integrating individual residential consumers into energy communities was carried out based on the current regulations in Spain. Scenarios explore the benefit of a variety of community coordination strategies to understand how self-consumption (individual vs. collective), the sale of renewables (no export, with export), as well as device selection (load only, load with PV, load with PV and batteries), sizing, and location affect the value of investing in renewable generation and storage. This study incorporates recent changes to collective self-consumption rules in Spain by introducing an hourly variable distribution coefficient. Results indicate that enabling collective self-consumption and the sale of excess generation has the highest potential to reduce the combined investment and operational costs. Engaging in only collective self-consumption results in the second lowest cost, and allowing only the sale of excess generation without self-consumption results in the third lowest cost. Given the assumptions of this study, there is a preference for installing only PV at the sites and not batteries.

Keywords:

Energy planning; Optimization; ECOS Conference; Energy communities; Self-consumption; system integration; techno-economic analysis.

1. Introduction

The concept of energy communities was first introduced in the European legislation through Clean Energy for all Europeans Package (CEP) where the Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) and Renewable Energy Communities (REC) and their applicable rules were described. These communities were intended to contribute to the CEP's goal of placing the consumer at the heart of the energy transition and help mobilize private financing for renewable energies, lower public resistance against the energy transition and enhance flexibility in electrical markets [1].

Through the recast Directive on common rules for the internal electricity market (Directive EU 2019/944) [2], the CEP also introduced the concepts of 'Active consumer', 'Renewables self-consumer' and 'Jointly active self-consumers', which covered individual and collective self-consumption activities. The last of these figures is defined as a group of at least two jointly acting renewable energy consumers for which this activity does not represent their primary commercial or professional activity, and will be referred as Collective Self-Consumption (CSC) throughout this paper as it is a more commonly adopted term. Although CSC, CEC and REC are defined separately in the European legislation, they share common characteristics that permit active consumers to engage in CSC inside the energy community framework of certain jurisdictions as explained in Frieden et al. [3].

Since the CEP publication, multiple studies have emerged analyzing the potential business models that communities could adopt within this framework and the expected challenges and benefits associated with their operation. For instance, Eichman et al., reviews a number of articles that explore the potential for energy communities (ECs) to increase the share of renewable energy generation, self-sufficiency, and flexibility of energy assets which, in turn, could provide environmental, social and economic benefits such as lower emissions, more equitable distribution of the energy transition gains, lower consumer costs, and lower systems costs and delayed grid expansions through the provision of flexibility services [4]. The latter is particularly

important given CEP's goal of having at least 40% of the EU's energy consumption covered by renewable energies by 2030 [3], which poses additional challenges for the electrical systems management and might represent higher costs for consumers if options like flexibility services are not available to operators.

To take advantage of EC's benefits, regulations incentivizing the proper development of EC must be put in place [5]. Otherwise, they might impose additional issues to the energy system or create unfair cost recovery structures. In fact, a key challenge for EC regulation is to ensure the cost-efficiency of these projects beyond locally-derived benefits [6]. The specific rules applicable to EC vary across EU members as each of them is responsible of developing its own framework to accommodate the guidelines established by the CEP associated legislation. Nonetheless, as stated in the Directive EU 2019/944, national EC regulations must allow their participation in all electrical markets [2]. This opens the door for different business models configurations that can help EC to make a sound economic case to invest in renewable energies for covering their own members' consumption, sharing with other citizens or ECs, or selling electricity or associated services in available markets.

Through the transposition of EU's CEP, Spain implemented self-consumption beginning with Real Decreto 15/2018, which regulates consumer protections and self-consumption, followed by Real Decreto 244/2019, which provided more complete guidance including connection strategies and limited connections to either a direct line between consumers, on the same distribution network or less than 500 meters between production and consumption facilities [7, 8]. There were changes to this framework in June 2021 with Real Decreto 477/2021 which introduced incentive programs for interested parties to participate in self-consumption [9]. In December 2021, Real Decreto 29/2021 was passed which allowed community members to be connected on low voltage or high voltage networks [10]. Lastly, hourly variable distribution coefficients were introduced in Order TED/1247/2021 [11]. Distribution coefficients determine how much production is shared with others participating in CSC. Prior to this regulation, entities could only introduce a static sharing coefficient which limited consumers' ability to maximize energy cost reductions from CSC.

Previous studies have already evaluated the economic case for different self-consumption configurations in Spain. For instance, Roldán Fernández et al. conducts a regional analysis of optimal self-consumption installations following the rules stated in Real Decreto 244/2019, showing that optimally sized photovoltaic (PV) systems lead to economic savings for Spanish customers in all regions [12]. That work also conducts a sensitivity analysis evaluating the potential usage of electrical batteries as part of the system's configuration, noticing that further cost reductions are needed to make its implementation profitable, particularly under surplus compensation mechanisms such as those contemplated in the current legislation. Similarly, Domenech et al. explored profitability of residential PV with storage in different cities, load profiles and for different objectives. The work conducted in Gallego-Castillo et al. evaluates the profitability of PV self-consumption for a typical Spanish dwelling considering different PV sizes and the compensation mechanisms [13]. The analysis found that the systems were more profitable when self-consumption was favored over selling excess energy to the grid. It also explains that utilizing CSC schemes might improve the economic case of the evaluated cases.

Spain is experiencing rapid changes to the regulations regarding energy communities and consumer coordination strategies. As such, there is a need to understand how the changes affect the value proposition for collective self-consumption and more generally energy communities. To the authors' knowledge, there are no studies that compare individual versus collective self-consumption configurations in Spain, and no studies that have explored the impact of the recent updates to CSC introduced by Order TED/1246/2021. Additionally, the collection of optimization and simulation studies in the literature are varied in the elements that are included. Some include time-varying energy prices, fixed costs for demand charges, compensation for excess generation, and storage. However, there are no studies that endeavor to include all of these items. This study includes all of the aforementioned features in an effort to explore the main drivers for value for different energy community configurations.

2. Approach

Due to the rapid changes in the regulatory framework surrounding collective self-consumption, there has yet to be an assessment of the potential for consumers that includes the new rules, namely variable distribution coefficient. The open-source Revenue Operation and Device Optimization (RODeO) model was used to perform the optimization of consumers for this study. RODeO is a mixed integer linear programming model with the objective to maximize the net present value over the study period of the system modelled [14]. RODeO already has the capability to model retail rate structures, various system configurations and technologies including on-site generation, storage, and loads (both flexible and inflexible), and it has a detailed financial model that includes taxes, asset depreciation, credits, and incentives [15]. The scenarios developed to explore the value of energy coordination between consumers are described in the next section, and updates made to RODeO to reflect the change to variable distribution coefficients for collective self-consumption and are discussed in Section 2.2.

2.1. Scenario development and assumptions

While consumers can participate in self-consumption and collective self-consumption with a variety of renewable energy generation technologies, the most common technology considered is fixed-tilt photovoltaic (PV) panels. In addition, consumers can decide on additional technologies to support their system including energy storage, and flexible loads. Consumers have the possibility to install PV, battery storage, or nothing. In addition, the consumers have the option to allow export of energy or prevent export. Those configurations are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Consumer configurations considered in the optimization analysis.

For the purpose of this paper, we examine communities that include eight consumers living in multi-unit dwellings. Each consumer follows the configurations in Figure 1 and have a unique load profile based on the family size and working status. These profiles were generated using the open-source LoadProfileGenerator [16]. Solar radiation data and temperature data were drawn from PVWatts for a location close to Barcelona, Spain [17] and the default parameters were used for the household properties. Information about the profiles is shown in Table 1 and the daily average profile for each household is presented in Figure 2.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the load profile of the eight selected households

Household number	Designation	Description	Maximum Power (kW)	Minimum Power (kW)	Average Power (kW)	Standard deviation of Power (kW)
1	CHR01	Couple both at work	6.59	0.103	0.617	0.792
2	CHR05	Family with 3 children, both parents work	3.76	0.045	0.594	0.589
3	CHR07	Working single person	3.94	0.046	0.205	0.370
4	CHR15	Multigenerational family with 2 working adults, 2 children and 2 seniors	7.82	0.100	1.382	1.233
5	CHR16	Couple over 65 years old	5.49	0.017	0.584	0.795
6	CHR22	Single working woman with 1 child	2.10	0.055	0.213	0.285
7	CHR40	Non-working couple (30-64 years old)	3.00	0.062	0.406	0.439
8	CHR52	Student sharing an apartment	4.08	0.052	0.426	0.489

Figure 2. Daily average power consumption profiles for each consumer (left axis) and total for all consumers (right axis).

Photovoltaic generation profiles are developed using the PVWatts model [17]. A location near Barcelona was chosen. In addition to the solar radiation and temperature information that was used in developing the load profiles, PVWatts provides alternating current (AC) and direct current (DC) power output. A fixed 20 degree tilt, 15% efficient, crystalline silicone panel was selected. Values presented for size are AC and include a 14.08% system loss, 96% inverter efficiency and a DC to AC ratio of 1.2. The annual capacity factor of the PV system is 18.2% if all the energy is used.

In addition to the five configurations depicted in Figure 1, the community of eight consumers can take service under one of five different retail electricity tariffs (shown in Table 2). The community can also engage in individual self-consumption (where they do not share renewable energy) or collective self-consumption (where they share renewable energy). In addition, scenarios that allow the sale of excess generation and prevent the sale of excess generation are considered. This sale price is set according to the self-consumption surplus energy price provided by RED Eléctrica de España under the voluntary price for the small consumer (PVPC) scheme.

If consumers are allowed to share under collective self-consumption, there is greater flexibility regarding the location and sizing of the installed equipment. We have developed several scenarios to explore these effects. For location, the PV or storage can be either 1.) distributed across the community based on the consumers' average energy consumption or 2.) concentrated in only the second and third households. Similarly, "Small" PV systems are sized at 75% of the annual average power consumption and "Large" systems are 50% of the peak annual power consumption. Comparing to the total load of all consumers, the renewable solar fraction (sum of annual solar generation divided by sum of annual load) is 13.6% for the small system with export and 13.5% without export allowed and 76.0% for the large system with export and 46.5% without export allowed.

For storage the "Small" systems are 20% of the annual average power and for "Large", they are 20% of the annual peak power consumption. This methodology establishes the installed power capacity and it is assumed that storage systems have an energy capacity of 4 hours at rated discharge power. That means that the small storage system is 0.89 kW with 3.56 kWh of storage capacity, and the large storage system is 7.4 kW with 29.6 kWh of storage capacity.

The technical assumptions, retail electricity rate information and financial assumptions are presented in Table 2. The chosen unit of currency is the Euro. The conversion rate of 0.89 Euros to 1 dollar is used to convert the capital and operation and maintenance costs to euros.

Table 2. Technoeconomic assumptions

Category	Parameter	Value	Ref.																																																											
Technical assumptions	PV capacity (kW of fixed tilt panels for each household modelled)	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Location</th> <th rowspan="2">Size</th> <th colspan="8">Consumer</th> </tr> <tr> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> <th>4</th> <th>5</th> <th>6</th> <th>7</th> <th>8</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Distributed</td> <td>Small</td> <td>0.5</td> <td>0.4</td> <td>0.2</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>0.4</td> <td>0.2</td> <td>0.3</td> <td>0.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Concentrated</td> <td>Small</td> <td></td> <td>1.6</td> <td>1.7</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Distributed</td> <td>Large</td> <td>3.3</td> <td>1.9</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>3.9</td> <td>2.7</td> <td>1.1</td> <td>1.5</td> <td>2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Concentrated</td> <td>Large</td> <td></td> <td>9.0</td> <td>9.4</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Location	Size	Consumer								1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Distributed	Small	0.5	0.4	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.3	Concentrated	Small		1.6	1.7						Distributed	Large	3.3	1.9	2.0	3.9	2.7	1.1	1.5	2.0	Concentrated	Large		9.0	9.4							
		Location			Size	Consumer																																																								
			1	2		3	4	5	6	7	8																																																			
		Distributed	Small	0.5	0.4	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.3																																																			
		Concentrated	Small		1.6	1.7																																																								
	Distributed	Large	3.3	1.9	2.0	3.9	2.7	1.1	1.5	2.0																																																				
	Concentrated	Large		9.0	9.4																																																									
	PV capital cost	\$1387/kW	[18]																																																											
	PV fixed operation and maintenance	\$10/kW-year	[18]																																																											
	Storage power capacity (kW for each household modelled)	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Location</th> <th rowspan="2">Size</th> <th colspan="8">Consumer</th> </tr> <tr> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> <th>4</th> <th>5</th> <th>6</th> <th>7</th> <th>8</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Distributed</td> <td>Small</td> <td>0.12</td> <td>0.1</td> <td>0.0</td> <td>0.28</td> <td>0.12</td> <td>0.04</td> <td>0.08</td> <td>0.09</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Concentrated</td> <td>Small</td> <td></td> <td>0.4</td> <td>0.5</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Distributed</td> <td>Large</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>0.8</td> <td>0.8</td> <td>1.6</td> <td>1.1</td> <td>0.4</td> <td>0.6</td> <td>0.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Concentrated</td> <td>Large</td> <td></td> <td>3.6</td> <td>3.8</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Location	Size	Consumer								1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Distributed	Small	0.12	0.1	0.0	0.28	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.09	Concentrated	Small		0.4	0.5						Distributed	Large	1.3	0.8	0.8	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.6	0.8	Concentrated	Large		3.6	3.8							
Location		Size			Consumer																																																									
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8																																																				
Distributed		Small	0.12	0.1	0.0	0.28	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.09																																																				
Concentrated		Small		0.4	0.5																																																									
Distributed	Large	1.3	0.8	0.8	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.6	0.8																																																					
Concentrated	Large		3.6	3.8																																																										
Storage energy capacity	4 hours at rated discharge power																																																													
Storage efficiency	85% AC to AC																																																													
Storage capital cost	955 \$/kWh †	[18]																																																												
Storage self-discharge	1% of stored energy per day	[19]																																																												
Retail electricity rates	Sale price	Related to wholesale market price	[20]																																																											
	Endesa - One Luz	Flat energy rate with timed demand charge	[21]																																																											
	Endesa - One Luz 3 period	Time-of-use energy rate with timed demand charge	[22]																																																											
	Hola Luz - Classic 10kW	Time-of-use energy rate with timed demand charge	[23]																																																											
	Hola Luz – Fair rate 10kW	Flat energy rate with timed demand charge	[23]																																																											
	Pepe Energy - ECO	Time-of-use utility rate with timed demand charge	[24]																																																											
	Euro to dollar	0.89 Euros to 1 dollar																																																												
Financial assumptions	Study period	20 years																																																												
	Tax rate	25%																																																												
	Equity	41.9%																																																												
	Debt interest rate	3.125%	[25]																																																											
	Inflation	1.6%																																																												
	Weighted average cost of capital	7%																																																												
	Depreciation schedule	10% for up to 20 years	[26]																																																											

† This price is based on behind-the-meter storage costs for France in 2020.

2.2. Modelling collective self-consumption

The main objective of RODEO is to maximize the net present value (NPV) over the study period which includes the operating profits ($Profit_t$), upfront capital investment, taxes ($Taxes_t$), and debts ($Debts_t$) (shown in Eq. (1)). This formulation has been explored in depth in Koleva et al. [15]. The optimization model is run hourly (h) for one year (TH_t) and it is assumed that the pricing signals and behaviour are similar each year (t) of the study period (T). WACC represents the weighted average cost of capital, $CapCost_{tech}$ is the capital cost for each technology, and Cap_{tech} is the installed capacity for each technology.

$$NPV = \sum_t (Profit_t - Taxes_t - Debts_t) / (WACC + 1)^t - \sum_{tech} (CapCost_{tech} \cdot Cap_{tech}), \forall t \in T \quad (1)$$

Where Operating profits consist of the value of electricity sold to the grid, the fixed and variable operation and maintenance cost, and the cost for importing electricity which is comprised of energy charge, demand charge, and equipment charge (e.g., for electricity meter and service) (shown in Eq. (2)).

$$Profit_t = infl_t \cdot \left(\sum_{h \in TH_t} (e_h^{sale} \cdot P_{h,g}^{Export} - e_h^{purchase} \cdot P_{h,g}^{Import}) - \sum_{m \in TM_t} (TDC_m \cdot \max_m(P_{h,g}^{Import}) + MMC_m) - \sum_{tech} (FOM_{tech} + VOM_{tech}) \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\forall t \in T$$

Where $infl_t$ is inflation for each year, e_h^{sale} is the hourly sale price for electricity and $e_h^{purchase}$ is the hourly purchase price. $P_{h,g}^{Export}$ represents the power exported to the grid for each consumer in the community (g), and $P_{h,g}^{Import}$ represents the power imported from the grid. In this study the chosen utility rates have either flat or time-of-use (TOU) energy charges and all have TOU demand charges. There are three TOU bins for the energy charges (peak, flat, and valley), and only two for TOU demand charges (peak and valley). The selected rates are aligned with Spain's Voluntary price for the small consumer (PVPC) time bins for the 2TD category. Circular 3/2020 describes the time periods [27]. TDC_m represents the TOU timed demand charge as a cost per kilowatt, $\max_m(P_{h,g}^{Import})$ represents the maximum power imported during the month in each TOU bin for each community, and MMC_m represents the monthly cost for metering and support. These values are calculated each month (m) over each month of the year (TM_t) Lastly, FOM_{tech} represents the fixed operation and maintenance cost for each technology and VOM_{tech} represents the variable operation and maintenance cost. One of the main contributions of this paper is the implementation of variable hourly distribution coefficients for collective self-consumption. This is done first by tracking the renewable and non-renewable contributions to the storage system and for sale to the grid (shown in Eq. (3)). This allows for the isolation of the renewable portion of several variables, which is used for individual self-consumption. By summing the PV generation power ($P_{h,g}^{PVgen}$) for all consumers (G), then multiplying by the hourly distribution coefficient ($C_{h,g}^{sharing}$) we can enable optimal sharing of each PV system between all consumers (shown in Eq. (4)). This means that any portion of the produced PV can be distributed to any of the consumers in each hour. In this way, Eq. (3) represents individual self-consumption, and Eq. (4) represents collective self-consumption.

$$Load_{h,g}^{ren} - P_{h,g}^{Storageoutren} + P_{h,g}^{Storageinren} + P_{h,g}^{Exportren} \leq P_{h,g}^{PVgen} \quad (3)$$

$$Load_{h,g}^{ren} - P_{h,g}^{Storageoutren} + P_{h,g}^{Storageinren} + P_{h,g}^{Exportren} \leq \left(\sum_{g \in G} P_{h,g}^{PVgen} \right) \cdot C_{h,g}^{sharing} \quad (4)$$

It is important to note that while collective self-consumption allows for the transfer of energy among consumers, each consumer must still contract the appropriate power level as if they were not engaged in collective self-consumption (i.e., the energy charges are calculated as if the PV generation is distributed as defined by the distribution coefficient, but the timed demand charge are calculated as if the PV generation cannot be distributed to other consumers).

3. Results

The optimization determines the maximum net present value (NPV) over the study period. This is particularly important when considering how to operate the energy storage. An example average annual output from the model is shown in Figure 3. The example in Figure 3 shows the power profiles on July 31st, for PV+Storage+Load with large, concentrated PV and storage systems, with the Pepe Energy Eco rate, and self-consumption and export enabled. With 180 scenarios, it is not practical to show a figure for each scenario so this example is included to provide the reader with an understanding of how the model operates and the resulting outputs.

The storage charges using PV during the afternoon and discharges during peak load times when there is limited PV generation and high energy prices. There is no import during the day when the energy prices are the highest. The optimization also has the ability to minimize the annual contracted power to improve the NPV. Lastly, there is a portion of the PV generation that is exported in this scenario because exports are enabled.

Figure 3. Modelled power profiles on July 31st, for PV+Storage+Load with large, concentrated PV and storage systems, on Pepe Energy Eco rate, with self-consumption and export enabled.

The most important indicator for this study is the NPV result. We can identify specific results by isolating the relevant parameters in which we are most interested. Overall, we want to understand the effect of 1.) the utility rate selected, 2.) self-consumption and sales of renewables, 3.) sizing and location of energy assets in the community. These topics are explored in subsequent sections. The complete table of NPV results is available in Appendix A.

3.1 Considerations for selection of utility rates

Comparing utility rates with different time-of-use bins is challenging because the actual bill strongly depends on the time which electricity is used. This is by design since differences in the prices are meant to be a signal to consumers to encourage them to reduce consumption or shift it from high price periods to low price periods. Two rates have flat energy costs and three other rates have time-of-use structures. Because each consumer needs to purchase electricity to meet their needs every year all of the NPV results will be negative, indicating the total amount of money spent over the 20-year study period. The results clearly show that Pepe Energy offers the lowest cost (highest NPV) while Hola Luz has the highest cost (lowest NPV) (shown in Table 3). The resulting NPV for the scenarios with Endesa rates are within 8% of the scenarios with Pepe Energy rates.

Table 3. Comparison of the Average NPV over the study period for each utility rate

	Pepe Energy ECO	Endesa One Luz 3 periods	Endesa One Luz	Hola Luz Fair Rate	Hola Luz Classic
Average NPV (thousand €)	-107.5	-115.0	-115.8	-156.8	-158.7
Count of scenarios	36	36	36	36	36

3.2 Considerations for self-consumption and sales of renewables

The main coordination strategies explored in this study are individual or collective self-consumption and whether to include or exclude the sales of excess renewable energy generation. By exploring the NPV and PV curtailment results for systems with each permutation of those items we can isolate the impact of each coordination strategy.

The results show that engaging in both collective self-consumption and allowing sales of renewables results in the highest NPV (lowest cost). Engaging in only collective self-consumption is the next most lucrative, with 82% of the benefit of the scenario with both self-consumption and sales of renewables. Allowing only sales of renewables provides 55% of the benefit. This means that most of the benefit can be accessed by accessing either collective self-consumption or sales of renewable generation.

Table 4. Comparison of the Average NPV and Curtailment over the study period for scenarios with collective self-consumption and the sales of renewables

Collective Self-Consumption Sales of renewable generation	Yes	Yes	No	No
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Average NPV (thousand €)	-122.0	-125.8	-131.8	-143.5
Percentage of benefits achieved	100%	82%	55%	0%
Curtailment (MWh)	0.0	3.1	0.0	7.8
Count of scenarios	45	45	45	45

Collective self-consumption or sales of renewable generation can reduce curtailment, but the curtailment is reduced the most by allowing the sales of excess renewable generation. This creates an interesting trade-off between curtailment and economic performance.

3.3 Considerations for device selection, sizing, and location

By comparing scenarios that use only install PV to those that install PV and battery and separating the size and location, we can draw conclusions about the conditions that affect the decision to install batteries (Table 5). Given the assumptions regarding cost of the battery, the electricity rate structures, and load shapes it is preferable not to install energy storage in nearly all cases. There is one exception for rates with high energy costs (Hola Luz Classic and Single). Installing a battery in the large distributed cases results in a lower cost than installing only the PV because the storage is able to reduce energy costs more significantly. For large, concentrated systems, if collective self-consumption and sales of renewables are not allowed, then the costs are very high because the oversized storage and PV are not able to be utilized to their potential. This situation can be addressed by appropriately sizing the PV systems so it is not likely to occur in real systems.

Table 5. Comparison of the Average NPV over the study period (thousand €) for device selection, sizing and location

Collective self-consumption			Yes	Yes	No	No
Sale of renewables			Yes	No	Yes	No
Devices	Size	Location				
PV	Large	Distributed	-95.6	-108.6	-103.3	-120.9
PV+Batt.	Large	Distributed	-97.4	-101.0	-102.9	-134.5
PV	Large	Concentrated	-97.4	-110.5	-129.7	-160.4
PV+Batt.	Large	Concentrated	-105.6	-110.0	-135.9	-154.9
PV	Small	Distributed	-135.7	-135.8	-137.4	-138.2
PV+Batt.	Small	Distributed	-139.3	-139.2	-139.5	-139.9
PV	Small	Concentrated	-136.4	-136.5	-143.4	-147.1
PV+Batt.	Small	Concentrated	-139.7	-139.6	-143.1	-145.1
	Load Only		-150.8	-150.8	-150.8	-150.8

Concentrating the installation of assets has the potential to reduce installation cost for the PV or storage. Having to go through the approval, system design, site preparation, and installation processes for many sites is likely to be more expensive than performing all of those steps at only one site. Particularly for the “small” systems, enabling collective self-consumption, brings the NPV values very close to the distributed values for PV and for PV with storage. This further reinforces the benefits of engaging in collective self-consumption.

Given the financial and other assumptions, large installations were found to have lower total NPV cost than small better except when no sales or no self-consumption is allowed. Additionally, only installing a storage system is not found to be competitive for any scenario. The storage system will not be able to access collective self-consumption or sales of renewables without installing an eligible generation asset. Thus the storage must rely on arbitrage and demand charge reduction to offset that added capital cost and round-trip efficiency loss of the storage.

Similar to the previous section, we can look at the curtailment that results from the installation of different combinations of devices (Table 6). In the cases where sales are not allowed, adding storage can reduce curtailment significantly. While installing a storage system was not seen to be cost competitive, if the priority

of the community is to increase the renewable production for consumers, then it would be preferable to install an energy storage system.

Table 6. Comparison of the Curtailment (MWh) for scenarios with PV and energy storage

Collective self-consumption Sale of renewables Devices	Yes	Yes	No	No
	Yes	No	Yes	No
PV	0.0	5.7	0.0	11.1
PV+Batt.	0.0	1.3	0.0	6.4

Conclusions

An assessment of the economic benefit of integrating individual residential consumers into energy communities was carried out based on the current regulations in Spain. Changes were introduced last year to the regulatory framework governing energy communities and self-consumption in Spain. This study implements an hourly variable distribution coefficient to reflect the regulatory changes to collective self-consumption. The purpose of this coefficient is to allow more control of the communities for how they share renewable energy. The result enables consumers in an energy community to increase the benefit of their renewable generation investment.

Scenarios were developed that captured benefit from a variety of configurations to understand how self-consumption (individual vs. collective), the sale of renewables (no export, with export), as well as device selection (load only, load with PV, load with PV and batteries), sizing, and location affect the value of investing in renewable generation and storage. Findings show that enabling collective self-consumption in accordance with the new rules in Spain and the sale of excess generation has the highest potential to reduce the combined investment and operational costs over the study period (i.e., NPV cost). Engaging in only collective self-consumption results in the second lowest NPV cost, though without allowing sale of excess generation there is potential for curtailment. Allowing only the sale of excess generation without self-consumption results in the third lowest NPV cost. These results indicate that for countries interested in encouraging energy communities, introducing rules that allow for collective self-consumption of renewable generation within a community is an important way to increase the benefit to the consumers. Similarly allowing for export of excess generation is an important way to both increase benefits to consumers and reduce curtailment, which can help to increase the renewable shares on the electric grid.

Installing PV or PV and batteries can reduce the costs for the community compared to scenarios with load only, given the assumptions in this study. While storage can enable opportunities to shift energy consumption to lower cost time periods and reduce demand charges, the added cost of the equipment was not offset by those benefits, so the most cost effective strategy was to install only PV.

The formulation introduced for the variable distribution coefficient can aid interested parties in understanding how to implement this new feature of collective self-consumption and the results of this paper can be used to help guide consumers interested in developing a community to make more informed decisions.

Future work

We would like to include an assessment for the impacts of site approval, design, preparation, and installation on the cost of distributed versus concentrated systems. This would allow for a more accurate comparison of the two systems. Additionally, we would like to expand the load scenarios to characterize more types of communities and we would also like to explore the impact of optimization under uncertainty particularly regarding load and renewable generation forecasting. This would mostly affect the storage runs, because the load with PV scenarios use fixed load profiles and fixed PV, the only impact that uncertainty would have on the “PV only” scenarios is with regard to the variable distribution coefficient. Most retail rate structures are predictable for months or years so they are not considered a source of uncertainty in this study. For the scenarios with storage, uncertainty will reduce the achievable cost reductions which could be important so we would like to capture those impacts for future studies.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 801342 (Tecniospring INDUSTRY) and from the Agència per a la Competitivitat de l’Empresa de la Generalitat de Catalunya. Cristina Corchero is a Serra Hunter Fellow.

Nomenclature

Indices

h	hour
t	year
$tech$	technology

Sets

H	Hour in a year
T	years of study period
TH_t	Hours in year t
TM_t	Months in year t

Scalar

$WACC$	Weighted Average Cost of Capital
--------	----------------------------------

Parameters

$CapCost_{tech}$	Capital cost for each technology [€/MW]
Cap_{tech}	Installed capacity for each technology [MW]
e_h^{sale}	Hourly sale price for electricity [€/kWh]
$e_h^{purchase}$	Hourly purchase price for electricity [€/kWh]
$infl_t$	Rate of inflation
$Load_{h,g}^{ren}$	Portion of hourly load for each consumer served by renewables [MW]

Variables

$C_{h,g}^{sharing}$	Hourly variable distribution coefficient for collective self-consumption
$Debts_t$	Debt from loan payment in year t [€]
FOM_{tech}	Fixed operation and maintenance [€]
MMC_m	Monthly meter cost [€/month]
NPV	Net present value of all consumers in community over the study period [€]
$P_{h,g}^{Export}$	Hourly power exported to the grid [MW]
$P_{h,g}^{Exportren}$	Renewable portion of power exported to the grid for each consumer [MW]
$P_{h,g}^{Import}$	Hourly power imported from the grid [MW]
$P_{h,g}^{PVgen}$	Hourly renewable generation for each consumer [MW]
$P_{h,g}^{Storageoutren}$	Renewable portion of storage discharge power for each consumer [MW]
$P_{h,g}^{Storageinren}$	Renewable portion of storage charge power for each consumer [MW]
$Profit_t$	Profit in year t [€]
$Taxes_t$	Taxes in year t [€]
TDC_m	Timed demand charge [€/(kW-month)]
VOM_{tech}	Variable operation and maintenance [€]

References

- [1] Achille Hannoset, Leen Peeters, and Andreas Tuerk, "Energy Communities in the EU - Task Force Energy Communities," BRIDGE HORIZON 2020, INTENSYS4EU, Dec. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/D3.12.d_BRIDGE_Energy-Communities-in-the-EU-3.pdf
- [2] *Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU*. 2019, pp. 125–199. [Online]. Available: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/944/oj>
- [3] D. Frieden *et al.*, "Are We on the Right Track? Collective Self-Consumption and Energy Communities in the European Union," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 22, p. 12494, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3390/su132212494.
- [4] J. Eichman, M. Torrecillas Castelló, and C. Corchero, "Reviewing and Exploring the Qualitative Impacts That Different Market and Regulatory Measures Can Have on Encouraging Energy Communities Based on Their Organizational Structure," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 6, p. 2016, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15062016.
- [5] Roland Tual *et al.*, "Deliverable 8.11 – Policy/Market Reform Recommendations Report - Final Version," FLEXCoop, 2018. [Online]. Available: https://uploads.strikinglycdn.com/files/2df7f845-35e5-447b-932d-deba7f35e8b0/FLEXCoop%20D8.1_Branding,%20Website%20and%20Social%20media%20channels_FINAL.pdf
- [6] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., *Energy communities: an overview of energy and social innovation*. LU: Publications Office, 2020. Accessed: Mar. 01, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/180576>
- [7] *Real Decreto-ley 15/2018, de 5 de octubre, de medidas urgentes para la transición energética y la protección de los consumidores*. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2018/10/05/15/con>
- [8] *Real Decreto 244/2019, de 5 de abril, por el que se regulan las condiciones administrativas, técnicas y económicas del autoconsumo de energía eléctrica*. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2019/04/05/244>
- [9] *Real Decreto 477/2021, de 29 de junio, por el que se aprueba la concesión directa a las comunidades autónomas y a las ciudades de Ceuta y Melilla de ayudas para la ejecución de diversos programas de incentivos ligados al autoconsumo y al almacenamiento, con fuentes de energía renovable, así como a la implantación de sistemas térmicos renovables en el sector residencial, en el marco del Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia*. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2021/06/29/477>
- [10] *Real Decreto-ley 29/2021, de 21 de diciembre, por el que se adoptan medidas urgentes en el ámbito energético para el fomento de la movilidad eléctrica, el autoconsumo y el despliegue de energías renovables*. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2021/12/21/29>
- [11] *Orden TED/1247/2021, de 15 de noviembre, por la que se modifica, para la implementación de coeficientes de reparto variables en autoconsumo colectivo, el anexo I del Real Decreto 244/2019, de 5 de abril, por el que se regulan las condiciones administrativas, técnicas y económicas del autoconsumo de energía eléctrica*. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/o/2021/11/15/ted1247>
- [12] J. M. Roldán Fernández, M. Burgos Payán, and J. M. Riquelme Santos, "Profitability of household photovoltaic self-consumption in Spain," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 279, p. 123439, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123439.
- [13] C. Gallego-Castillo, M. Heleno, and M. Victoria, "Self-consumption for energy communities in Spain: A regional analysis under the new legal framework," *Energy Policy*, vol. 150, p. 112144, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112144.
- [14] J. Eichman, A. Townsend, and M. Melaina, "Economic Assessment of Hydrogen Technologies Participating in California Electricity Markets," NREL/TP--5400-65856, 1239543, Feb. 2016. doi: 10.2172/1239543.
- [15] M. Koleva, O. J. Guerra, J. Eichman, B.-M. Hodge, and J. Kurtz, "Optimal design of solar-driven electrolytic hydrogen production systems within electricity markets," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 483, p. 229183, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.229183.
- [16] Noah Pflugradt, *LoadProfileGenerator*. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.loadprofilegenerator.de/>
- [17] *PVWatts®*. 2021.
- [18] IRENA, "Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2020," International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, 2021.

- [19] E. Redondo-Iglesias, P. Venet, and S. Pelissier, "Measuring Reversible and Irreversible Capacity Losses on Lithium-Ion Batteries," in *2016 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*, Hangzhou, China, Oct. 2016, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/VPPC.2016.7791723.
- [20] RED Eléctrica de España, "Sistema de información del operador del sistema (esios)," *Self-consumption surplus energy price for the simplified compensation mechanism (PVPC)*. https://www.esios.ree.es/en/analysis/1739?vis=1&start_date=18-03-2022T00%3A00&end_date=18-03-2022T23%3A00&compare_start_date=17-03-2022T00%3A00&groupby=hour&compare_indicators=1013,1014,1015 (accessed Mar. 01, 2022).
- [21] Endesa, "One Luz Tariff: tariff with a fixed price per kWh." <https://www.endesa.com/en/catalog/light/one/one-luz>
- [22] Endesa, "One Luz 3 Periodos Tariff." <https://www.endesa.com/en/catalog/light/one/tarifa-one-luz-3periodos-en> (accessed Mar. 01, 2022).
- [23] holaluz, "Electricity tariffs 100% green for your home." <https://www.holaluz.com/en/electricity-rates/#tarifaJusta> (accessed Mar. 01, 2022).
- [24] PepeEnergy, "La Tarifa ECO de Luz." <https://www.pepeenergy.com/tarifas-luz> (accessed Mar. 01, 2022).
- [25] Banco de España, "Table of banks' lending and borrowing rates." https://clientebancario.bde.es/pcb/en/menu-horizontal/productoservici/relacionados/tiposinteres/guia-textual/tiposinteresprac/Tabla_de_tipos__a0b053c69a40f51.html (accessed Mar. 01, 2022).
- [26] infoautónomos, "¿Qué son las amortizaciones? ¿Cómo funcionan? Ejemplo." <https://www.infoautonomos.com/contabilidad/tablas-de-amortizacion-para-los-bienes-de-una-empresa/> (accessed Mar. 01, 2022).
- [27] *Circular 3/2020, de 15 de enero, de la Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y la Competencia, por la que se establece la metodología para el cálculo de los peajes de transporte y distribución de electricidad*. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/cir/2020/01/15/3>

Appendix A

Table A.1 contains a complete set of NPV results from the scenarios in this study.

Table A.1. NPV over the study period (€) for all scenarios modelled

Utility Rate	Self Con	Ren. Sales	Load Only	PV Dist. Large	PV Dist. Small	PV Concen. Large	PV Concen. Small	PV+Batt Dist. Large	PV+Batt Dist. Small	PV+Batt Concen. Large	PV+Batt Concen. Small
Endesa1	0	0	-130.4	-120.8	-128.1	-109.8	-142.3	-123.1	-121.9	-138.3	-126.7
Endesa1	0	1	-130.4	-119.9	-124.4	-92.1	-111.6	-94.0	-121.4	-119.1	-124.3
Endesa1	1	0	-130.4	-118.9	-119.6	-100.0	-102.2	-96.1	-121.2	-103.6	-122.0
Endesa1	1	1	-130.4	-118.7	-119.4	-86.7	-89.0	-91.6	-121.1	-99.2	-121.8
Endesa3	0	0	-129.2	-119.4	-126.9	-108.4	-141.2	-133.7	-121.2	-137.5	-125.0
Endesa3	0	1	-129.2	-118.6	-123.2	-90.7	-110.4	-93.5	-120.7	-118.3	-123.3
Endesa3	1	0	-129.2	-117.5	-118.2	-98.5	-100.7	-93.6	-120.9	-102.6	-121.4
Endesa3	1	1	-129.2	-117.3	-118.1	-85.3	-87.5	-89.6	-120.7	-97.9	-121.3
HolaLuzClassic10	0	0	-187.7	-170.1	-181.6	-142.1	-193.4	-159.1	-172.9	-185.0	-179.0
HolaLuzClassic10	0	1	-187.7	-169.3	-178.0	-124.8	-162.7	-121.1	-172.6	-166.4	-177.1
HolaLuzClassic10	1	0	-187.7	-166.9	-167.5	-125.9	-127.5	-114.1	-172.4	-123.6	-172.1
HolaLuzClassic10	1	1	-187.7	-166.9	-167.4	-113.2	-114.8	-111.3	-172.7	-119.7	-172.5
HolaLuzSingle10	0	0	-185.3	-168.8	-179.6	-142.7	-191.5	-139.6	-169.5	-182.8	-176.6
HolaLuzSingle10	0	1	-185.3	-168.0	-175.9	-125.4	-160.8	-118.2	-169.2	-164.1	-174.6
HolaLuzSingle10	1	0	-185.3	-165.8	-166.4	-127.4	-129.0	-113.8	-168.3	-124.7	-168.9
HolaLuzSingle10	1	1	-185.3	-165.8	-166.3	-114.7	-116.2	-110.8	-168.3	-120.8	-168.9
PepeECO	0	0	-121.7	-112.1	-119.4	-101.4	-133.8	-117.1	-113.9	-131.0	-118.2
PepeECO	0	1	-121.7	-111.2	-115.7	-83.6	-103.0	-87.9	-113.5	-111.8	-116.0
PepeECO	1	0	-121.7	-110.1	-110.7	-91.4	-92.9	-87.4	-113.2	-95.3	-113.8
PepeECO	1	1	-121.7	-110.0	-110.5	-78.0	-79.5	-83.7	-113.7	-90.4	-113.9